

Plugin Installation Guide

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Pre-requisites

Make sure to have Chrome installed and updated to version **99.0.4844.74**.

Please go [here](#) to install Chrome.

Installing the plugin

1. Go to:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iefBIMJrI90RxRr-VzGkJj0XtlpXyDi6/view?usp=sharing>
and download all files.

2. Unzip the file on your computer.
3. Open Google Chrome and type 'chrome://extensions' (no quotation marks) in the address bar.
4. Check the option "Enable developer mode".

5. Select the button that says 'Load unpacked' on the top left corner and select the unzipped folder you downloaded -> (ResearchPlugin -> **ChromeExtension**).

6. You should now see the plugin 'Research Plugin', in the top left corner.

7. Restart Chrome.
8. Finish the installation here - The plugin is ready to use.

Updating the Plugin

If you already have the plugin installed and want to update it to the newest version, repeat the same steps above to install the plugin and then press the “Update” button to refresh your extensions.

Using the Extension

If the plugin needs to be removed from the current page, click the button in the top right of the Chrome browser. The menu below should appear:

To remove the plugin from the current page, click the green button in the pop up menu.

Uninstalling the Extension

To remove the extension from the browser, go to `chrome://extensions` and click on the "Remove" button under the Research Plugin.

